

TRADITIONAL DISHES IN DIFFERENT CULTURE

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Abstract: This article represents a lot of information about important food in various culture from past to now. Moreover, we may know history of food by reading this article. Especially, there are some types of traditional food and they can differentiate from one another due to their cultures. In this article, the culture of dishes in Germany, Greece, Karakalpakstan, and Turkey, and their difference you may learn.

Key words: Germany: Swabian ravioli/Maultaschen, Dresden fruit loaf/Dresdener Stollen Pumpernickel bread/Pumpernickel Brot, Thuringian fried sausage/Thüringer Rostbratwurst, Greece: Cherry tomato of Santorini, Chickpea soup, Must jelly, Karakalpakstan: Pilaf, gurtik, manti, Juweri gurtik, Turkey: Anchovy stew, Kebab with yogurt, Baklava.

Introduction

Traditions are customs or beliefs taught by one generation to the next, often by word of mouth, and they play an important role in cultural identification. Each culture, ethnic group or region has specific traditions. Some traditions, such as religious customs, overlap different cultures, ethnic groups or regions.

Specific eating habits play an important role in the traditional habits of many cultures. The use of particular food ingredients and food preparation methods has been passed on from one generation to the next, and are nowadays referred to as “traditional foods”. Traditional foods have played a major role in traditions of different cultures and regions for thousands of years. They include foods that have been consumed locally and regionally for an extended time period. Preparation methods of traditional

foods are part of the folklore of a country or a region. Unfortunately, some countries, some traditional foods are at risk of disappearing due to altered lifestyles. Therefore, it is important to study and document traditional foods to sustain important elements of countries cultures.

Discussion

Although the term “traditional foods” is widely used, and everybody has a rough idea of what is meant by it, there are hardly any definitions that clearly define traditional foods. So, we need to pay attention below definition.

Traditional means conforming to established practice or specifications prior to the Second World War. Traditional food is a food with a specific feature or features, which distinguish it clearly from other similar products of the same category in terms of the use of ‘traditional ingredients’ (raw materials of primary products) or ‘traditional composition’ or ‘traditional type of production and/or processing method’ as defined below.

Raw material (species and/or varieties) or primary product, either alone or as an ingredient, which has been used in identifiable geographical areas and remains in use today (considering cases where use was abandoned for a time and then reinstated) and its characteristics are in accordance with current specifications of national and EU legislation.

The uniquely identifiable composition (in terms of ingredients) that was first established prior to the Second World War and passed down through generations by oral or other means (considering cases where composition was abandoned for a time and then reinstated) and when necessary is differentiated from the composition defined by the generally recognised characteristics of the wider food group to which the product belongs.

Traditional type of production and/or processing

The production and/or processing of a food that:

- Has been transmitted from generation to generation through oral tradition or other means

- Has been applied prior to the Second World War and remains in use (taking into account cases where composition was abandoned for a time and then reinstated) despite its adjustment to binding rules from national or EU food hygiene regulations or the incorporation of technological progress, under the condition that production and/or processing remains in line with methods used originally and that the food's intrinsic features such as its physical, chemical, microbiological or organoleptic features are maintained.

When speaking about the traditional cuisine of a country, we actually refer to something that is rather diverse. There are some foods and dishes that may be traditional across a whole country, but usually a variety of local traditional foods exist. Thus, the traditional cuisine of a country includes and reflects a collection of traditional foods from different regions. The vegetable stew Ratatouille for example originates from the south of France, whereas the famous Crêpes originally came from Brittany. However, both dishes are nowadays widely consumed across the whole country, and – in the context of the Euro FIR definition of traditional foods – they are considered traditional foods consumed throughout France, although they originate from a more restricted geographical area. Over time, traditional foods have been influenced by many factors. One of these factors is the availability of raw materials; traditional food is thus influenced by agricultural habits and location. Regions at a lower altitude, for example, have different vegetation compared to regions at high altitudes; countries without access to the sea usually have a lower availability of fish and seafood compared to those with a large coastal area. However, not only the location of a region, but also its history has influenced the dietary patterns of its inhabitants.

The discovery of the New World and the development of international trade, and thus the availability of foods that had not been previously available, have also influenced traditional foods across Europe. Potatoes for example – nowadays the basis of many European traditional dishes – first found their way to Europe from South America in the 16th century, started to spread across Europe in the 18th century, and potato cultivation reached its peak in the 19th century [1].

Also, other foods that are nowadays frequently used ingredients of many European traditional dishes were introduced from the New World, such as maize, sunflowers, pumpkins (marrows), sweet potatoes, Jerusalem artichoke, vanilla, and tomatoes – a fruit now found in many traditional Mediterranean dishes. Traditional foods and dishes have also been influenced by religious habits and beliefs. Certain culinary rules have always been a part of different religions. In Europe, where Christians, Muslims and Jewish people have lived next to each other for centuries, each religion has defined itself in terms of diet and food taboos [2: 11-37].

Although playing an important role in cultural identity, traditional foods have experienced continuous modifications, which reflect the history of a country or a region. Now let's consider some countries traditional dishes and as a result we will know a lot of information about them.

Traditional German cuisine

Germany is the most populous country in the European Union with more than 80 million inhabitants. The German territory has not always been one single country but for many centuries it consisted of numerous small units, such as principalities, petty kingdoms, cities, counties and dioceses. Thus, it is not surprising that there is no such thing as “German cuisine”. Germany has a variety of regional cuisines. The traditional cuisine of the south-west includes plenty of white bread and noodles, whereas many traditional dishes of the Baltic Sea coast include potatoes and a variety of spices and seasonings. Fish has been very popular along the Baltic and North Sea coasts and can be found in many traditional dishes, while traditionally fish has not been consumed in any quantity in regions further away from the sea. In Bavaria the traditional cuisine is rich in meat and meat products, in particular pork. These regional differences seem to be less obvious in the eating habits of Germans today. The different regions across Germany were influenced by the countries surrounding it. The traditional cuisine in the north-west of Germany was influenced by the Belgian cuisine, whereas the east shows Polish influences, and in the regions close to the Czech border influences of the Czech cuisine can be found [3:183-194]. Many Bavarian dishes are similar to dishes

commonly consumed in Austria. The cuisines across Germany are generally rich in meat. In particular, sausages are very popular and can be considered a German “fast food”. A variety of sausages with different seasonings and flavors are available throughout the country. Germany is also known for its variety of breads, which are an important component of the German diet. The breads are typically based on rye and/or wheat and are rather solid and dark. Apple desserts, such as apple cake, apple pancakes and apple strudel are popular. Stollen (sweetened yeast bread containing nuts and fruit) and Lebkuchen (richly spiced ginger biscuits sweetened with honey) are commonly consumed at Christmas time.

Swabian ravioli/Maultaschen

Maultaschen are a Swabian specialty with centuries of tradition. There are many legends around their origin, which have been passed on orally from generation to generation, and have been fixed in text only recently. Maultaschen are quadratic or half-moon in shape and comprise two-layer pasta dough forming a bag. They are usually filled with seasoned ground meat and spinach.

Dresden fruit loaf/Dresdener Stollen

Baking a fruit loaf is an old tradition in Dresden, a city situated in the east of Germany. The history of the Stollen can be traced back to the 14th century. It is typically made around Christmas and symbolises Jesus wrapped in a blanket. The Dresdner Stollen is a sweet Christmas pastry, made of yeast dough, raisins, almonds, candied lemon and orange peel.

Pumpernickel bread/Pumpernickel Brot

Pumpernickel bread is one of the most famous and typical German breads. It has been baked in the North-Rhine Westphalia region for centuries. It is made from sourdough based on rye, and it is extremely dark and aromatic.

Thuringian fried sausage/Thüringer Rostbratwurst

The Thüringer Rostbratwurst was first mentioned in 1432, where butchers proposed a law of ‘purity requirements’ for several sausages. The Thüringer

Rostbratwurst is a long (20 cm), thin (2.6-2.8 cm diameter) fried sausage made of natural gut filled with pork meat.

Traditional Greek cuisine

Greece has been a cross roads of people and civilisations for millennia, and this together with the climate has shaped the Greek cuisine. Traditional Greek dishes can be traced back to ancient Greece, the Hellenistic and the Byzantine periods. Greek cuisine has also incorporated influences from other civilisations, such as the Persian, the Roman and the Ottoman food cultures. Many names of Greek dishes reveal Turkish, Arabic or Persian sources, such as Moussaka, Baklava, Tzatziki or Keftethes. Some of these dishes, however, may have existed prior to the Ottoman times, but given a Turkish name later on. Modern Greek cuisine is an integral part of the past and the present, with many of its aspects traced in the traditional practices of distant times. The traditional Greek diet is generally considered to be healthy. The cultivation of fruit, vegetables, legumes and cereals is favoured and, therefore, these foods are consumed in large amounts. Olive oil is a staple food used with most meals, often in abundant amounts. Fish and seafood are consumed frequently, particularly in the coastal regions and on the numerous Greek islands. Meat, predominantly lamb, goat or pork, has in the past been consumed mainly on special occasions, although now intake has increased considerably. Wine is an important part of the Greek lifestyle, and is consumed regularly but in moderation, most often as a part of a meal. Dairy products are usually consumed in the form of cheese and yogurts; feta cheese is a world famous traditional Greek food.

Cherry tomato of Santorini

The cherry tomato was introduced to the island of Santorini at the end of the 19th century. The local environment, the genetic profile of the specific cherry tomato plant and the empirical agricultural methods developed by the inhabitants of the area contributed to the production of a distinctive food commodity widely used in a variety of ways in the contemporary local cuisine.

Chickpea soup

The cultivation of chickpeas in Greece goes back to the 3rd – 4th millennium BC, and ever since, chickpeas have been prepared and eaten in various ways. The chickpea soup represents a recipe widely known throughout Greece today. The main ingredients are chickpeas, water, onions, olive oil and lemon juice.

Must jelly

Fresh must, collected by pressing grapes, can be used either for wine-making or, after a process known as the ‘cutting’ of the must, for the preparation of a variety of sweet dishes such as marmalades, spoon sweets, Petimezi (thick syrup of condensed must), must cookies and must jelly. This must jelly is made from ‘cut’ must, semolina, almonds, flavoured with cinnamon and topped with sesame seeds.

Traditional Karakalpak cuisine

Karakalpak cuisine is an interesting mix of culinary arts of many Central Asian peoples: Uzbeks, Turkmens, Kazakhs. Like many other peoples of Central Asia, Karakalpaks cook **pilaf, shurpa, manti** (oriental dumplings) and many other oriental dishes. Of course, the Karakalpak food has its own peculiarities.

Among meat dishes, Karakalpaks eat beef, lamb, horse meat, rabbit meat and poultry. Usually, the main dishes are cooked of beef and lamb. The Karakalpaks are Muslims, they do not eat pork dishes. Corn, millet, rice, beans and other cereals are served as garnish to the first and second meals. A lot of potatoes and vegetables are consumed. Often Karakalpak food is a mixture of roasted meat with boiled dough. The most popular dishes are **gurtik, pilaf, shavlya, manti, samsa, dumplings, mastava soup, noodle soup** in a broth. Almost all dishes are served with bread made from wheat flour. Meal washed down with tea and milk. This custom was prevalent even among the nomads of the Middle Ages, and today it exists not only in the culture of Karakalpaks, but also of the Kazakhs and Turkmens. **Juweri gurtik** (dumplings) and **may gurtik** (oil gurtik) are one of the most popular Karakalpak foods. These dishes are old, but today often cooked by Karakalpak women. There is one more traditional Karakalpak dish with dumplings - **turama** (chop). These are finely crumbled meat with dumplings. The boiled meat is finely crumbled by adult males, while the

dumplings are crumbled by the present. After this, finely crumbled meat and dumplings are mixed. A bowl of turama top filled with broth is served for three or more people. Duzlik seasoning is served with turama. It is a mixture of chopped onions with the broth fat Karakalpak turama is a unique dish which is not typical of the cuisine of other Central Asian countries.

Traditional Turkish cuisine

Turkey is a cross roads between different cultures and regions, with borders to Central Asia, the Middle East and the Balkan region. Over the centuries, traditional Turkish cuisine has had many different influences. The Turks were originally from Central Asia and migrated towards Asia Minor, where they were influenced by the Persian culture. Once they settled in Asia Minor, the Turks were influenced by other cultures that had been there before. Hittites and Byzantines left their traces in the Turkish cuisine, influencing not only their food habits but also their kitchen utensils. New foods of Mediterranean origin, such as legumes or vegetables (cabbage, cauliflower or parsley) were introduced. Later, the Ottoman Empire, which lasted for more than 600 years, also influenced Turkish cuisine considerably. The most rapid progress in Turkish cuisine was observed during the reign of Fatih Sultan Mehmet (Mehment II the Conqueror). The Islamic religion has also considerably influenced the Turkish cuisine. Pork is forbidden by the Koran, and so is alcohol. Also other foods, such as reptiles, frogs and foxes, are forbidden. When the Turks accepted Islam as their religion, there was a clear Arabic influence; in particular, the south and south-east of Anatolia were influenced by Arabic cuisine [5]. The Turkish cuisine has some common specialties that can be found throughout the country, but taken as a whole it is not homogeneous. In the eastern region with its highlands, livestock farming is prevalent. Here, butter, yoghurt, cheese, honey, meat and cereals are local foods. The heartland of the Turkish region is dry steppe with endless stretches of wheat fields, and its cuisine includes dishes such as Kebab, Bırek, meat and vegetable dishes, and Helva desserts. The temperate climate in the western parts of Turkey allows the cultivation of a variety of fruits and vegetables, and also olives; olive oil is thus a staple and used in both hot

and cold dishes. The cuisine of northern Turkey is very much influenced by its adjacency to the Black Sea; a small fish similar to the anchovy, the Hamsi, can be found in many traditional dishes of this region. The hot and desert-like south-eastern part of Turkey offers the greatest variety of kebabs and sweet pastries; the dishes here are spicier. The traditional foods of the south-western regions in Turkey – including Marma, the Mediterranean and the Aegean – show basic characteristics of the Mediterranean cuisine; they are rich in fruits, vegetables, fish and lamb [6:443-457]. Many Turkish traditional dishes, such as Pilaf, use currants, cinnamon, pine nuts, chilli peppers, mint, parsley, dill or cumin as flavourings of meats and seafood. Tarhana, rice, lentil and offal soups are very popular. There is a variety of vegetables grown across Turkey, including aubergines, artichokes, beans, beetroot, chard, chick peas, cucumbers, mushrooms, onions, peppers, spinach and tomatoes. One popular way to consume these vegetables is as Dolmas (stuffed vegetables) consumed with yogurt.

Anchovy stew

Hamsi (anchovy) is one of the most economically important fish species of the Black Sea. There are various ways to consume Hamsi in the traditional Turkish cuisine, and buğulama (stewing) is one of the favourites. Hamsi buğulama is made with Hamsi, tomatoes, potatoes, onions, and lemon, cooked with olive oil and served as a main dish for lunch or dinner.

Kebab with yogurt

Kebab with yoghurt is one of the best known meat dishes of north-western Turkey. It is a kind of kebab prepared from thinly cut grilled meat served with tomato sauce over pieces of Pide bread and a generous amount of melted butter and yogurt.

Baklava

Baklava is one of the most famous Turkish desserts and is consumed throughout the country. The dough of this sweet pastry is made of wheat flour and eggs; the filling is a mixture of sugar, semolina, milk and pistachios. Before baking, melted butter is poured over the Baklava.

Conclusion

To sum up, in different countries, every traditional dishes are essential part in culture. In addition, they show us their culture and history. Therefore, we should know and respect other countries culture because of the fact that all of countries in the world can differentiate from another by culture.

References:

1. Toussaint-Samat M., History of food (Histoire naturelle et morale de la nourriture). Translated by Anthea Bell, English version published 1992; BORDAS, Paris. 1987.
2. Parasecoli F., Introduction. In: Culinary cultures of Europe. Identity, diversity and dialogue. Council of Europe Publishing, Verlagsgruppe Lubbe, Germany. 2005.
3. Hirschfelder G., Schonberger G.U., Germany. Sauerkraut, beer and so much more. In: Culinary cultures of Europe. Identity, diversity and dialogue. Council of Europe Publishing, Verlagsgruppe Lubbe, Germany. 2005.
4. <https://www.advantour.com/uzbekistan/karakalpakstan/karakalpak-food.htm>
5. Baysal A., Merdol T.K., Tasci N.C., Sacir F.H., Basoglu S. Samples from Turkish cuisine. Food Safety Department, Community Nutrition Division, Ministry of Health, Republic of Turkey, Ankara. 2006.
6. Sancar F.H., The tastes of a splendid heritage. In: Culinary cultures of Europe. Identity, diversity and dialogue. Council of Europe Publishing, Verlagsgruppe Lubbe, Germany. 2005.
7. Мусаев А. А. Паремнологик бирикмаларда ифодаланадиган каузатив тузилмаларнинг лингвомаданий хусусиятлари // Problems and scientific solutions. Australia, Melbourne, 2022. 169-175 б.